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An Experimental Study on structural behavior of sisal fiber using self- compacting concrete in addition to Glenium Stream 2

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ABSTRACT

Self-Compacting concrete is a type of concrete, which is not a product of mixing substances having different properties but a combination of several mix having the same flow characteristics. This project presents a comparative study between conventional concrete and self-compacting fibre-reinforced concrete (SCFRC) incorporating sisal fibres. Concrete produced with Portland cement exhibits specific mechanical properties: it has high compressive strength but relatively low tensile strength. This deficiency in tension can be addressed using traditional steel reinforcement and, to some extent, by incorporating an adequate quantity of fibres. Fibre-reinforced concrete (FRC) is a composite material composed of a cementitious matrix with uniformly distributed fibres, which may include steel, nylon, polyethylene, or other materials. The self-compacting nature of the concrete improves its performance in the fresh state, while the inclusion of fibres enhances its mechanical properties in the hardened state. In this study, a hybrid combination of banana and sisal fibres is used. Fibres employed in FRC may be derived from natural sources or manufactured materials such as glass, steel, carbon, or polymers. The fibres used for FRC can be natural material or artificial fibre such as glass, steel, carbon and polymer. Self-compacting concrete offers several technical benefits as well as economic benefits, the use of fibres extends possibilities.

Keywords: *Self compacting concrete, fibre, fibre reinforced concrete, self-consolidating concrete, banana fibre, sisal fibre*

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced concrete is a type of concrete that incorporates fibrous materials to enhance its structural performance. It consists of small, discontinuous fibres that are evenly dispersed and randomly aligned throughout the concrete matrix. Sisal fibre reinforced concrete is composed of concrete, reinforced with sisal fiber to produce a thin, yet strong material.

Though concrete has been used throughout ages SFRC is still a relatively new invention. High compressive and flexural strengths to reproduce fine surface details, low maintenance requirements, low coefficients of thermal expansion, high fire resistance and environmentally friendly made SFRC the ideal choice for civil engineers. The strength of SFRC is determined by fiber size, fiber compaction, distribution and orientation.[1]

Self-compacting concrete is the special type of concrete that is able to flow and consolidate its own weight without any external vibration. It has smooth surface level after placing. SSC consists of the same components as conventional and mineral admixtures. Usually, the chemical admixtures used are super plasticizers and viscosity modifying agents. The following are the guidelines for mix proportioning of SCC,[2]

1. Reducing the volume ration of aggregate to cementations material
2. Increasing the paste volume and water cement ration
3. Carefully regulate the overall volume and maximum coarse aggregate particle size
4. Using super plasticizers and viscosity modifying agents.

The initial modification to the concrete mix involves lowering the proportion of coarse aggregate to minimize inter-particle

friction. Typically, coarse aggregate should make up about 30–40% of the total mix volume. In addition, fine materials or fillers are incorporated to fill voids within the mix

SELF-COMPACTING CONCRETE

Self-compacting concrete is a special type of concrete that can flow and consolidate under its own weight. It is highly flowing able type concrete that does not require any mechanical compaction. The highly flowable nature of the SCC makes it suitable for placing in it difficult conditions such as tunnel constructions, underwater constructions and in sections with congested reinforcement. The use of self-compacting concrete can reduce the noise and its related damages on worksite that are induced by vibrating process of concrete. SSC helps to reduce the time of constructions of large areas of the buildings.[3]

In essence, self-compacting concrete (SCC) must exhibit adequate flowability to completely fill structural components, along with sufficient viscosity to prevent the segregation and settlement of coarse aggregate, thereby maintaining mix uniformity. However, conventional SCC generally has low tensile strength, limited ductility, and minimal resistance to cracking.

Micro-cracks naturally exist within the concrete, and the propagation of these cracks under tensile stress results in brittle failure. This inherent limitation can be significantly reduced by incorporating fibres into the concrete mixture. The presence of fibres improves crack resistance, enhances mechanical performance, and broadens the potential applications of SCC.[4]

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the evaluation between conventional concrete and self-compacting

fibre reinforced concrete on different properties of concrete.

2. To increase the strength properties of concrete by addition of natural fiber (sisal fiber)
3. To study the properties of sisal fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete.
4. Self-compacting concrete mixes are produced by addition of sisal fiber of 0%, 0.25%, 0.75%, 1.00%, 1.25% and 1.5%.
5. To assess the fresh and harden properties of self-compacting concrete(M30) with sisal fibers.
6. To learn the various workability properties of SCC such as U box, l box, V-funnel, j-ring to the mix
7. Testing the flow and passing ability of SCC and SCFRC.

PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS

The locally available manufacture of sand was used as fine aggregate in the present investigations. The sand was free from clayey matter, salt organic impurities. The specific gravity of fine aggregate is 2.6, fineness modulus of fine aggregate is 2.69 and bulk density of aggregate is 1697Kg/m^3 according to IS 2386-1963 test.[5]

The specific gravity of coarse aggregate is 2.62, water absorption is 8%, Crushing strength is 33% and Bulk density of coarse aggregate is 1580kg/m^3

The Specific gravity is 3.15. The physical properties such as consistency, initial

setting time and fineness and their corresponding values are 33%, 40 min and 5% respectively.

FRESH CONCRETE TEST RESULT

Fresh concrete, also known as plastic concrete, is newly mixed material that can be shaped or moulded into various sizes and forms. The proportions of cement, aggregates, and water used in the mix govern the properties of concrete in both its fresh state and after hardening. SCC must have the following characteristics in fresh state, Workability, filling ability, passing ability and high resistance to segregation.[6,7]

V-Funnel Test

V-funnel test is used to determine the filling ability of the SCC. The test results show that the time taken for lower replacement of fiber is much higher. Ability of flow is restricted due to addition of higher volume of fibers. The time taken for flow down the concrete as shown in figure 1. Minimum time for the flow of the entire concrete dumped in the V-Funnel is 6 seconds and maximum time to fall completely is 12 seconds.

The 0.25% of addition of sisal fiber in conventional concrete gives more filling ability compared to other mixes. The addition of higher percentage of fiber reduces workability. To enhance workability, an excess amount of water is required.[8,9]

Fig. 1: Time taken for flow down.

V-Funnel test was carried out for different proportions. The above graph shows that SC1 gives better results compared to other mix proportions.

L Box Test

The test accesses the flow of concrete, and the extent to which the concrete is subjected to blocking by reinforcement. If

the concrete flows as freshly as water, it will be horizontal. Therefore H_2/H_1 equals 1. The blocking ration is minimum acceptable value of 0.8. The blocking ratio of self-compacting concrete is reduced when increasing the addition of fiber of concrete. The L box results are shown in fig 2.

Fig. 2: L box Results.

L-Box test is carried out for various mix proportions. Thus, the L-Box test value is constantly decreasing with increasing fiber percentage.[10,11]

U-Box Test

The U-Box test is conducted to evaluate the filling ability of self-compacting concrete. Approximately 20 liters of

concrete are required for this test. Reinforcing bars with a nominal diameter of 13 mm are positioned at the gate with a center-to-center spacing of 50 mm, resulting in a clear gap of 35 mm between the bars. The concrete is initially placed in the left compartment, after which the gate is opened to allow the concrete to flow into the right compartment. The heights of

the concrete in both sections are then measured. If the concrete flows freely, similar to water, the resulting surface will be nearly level. The difference in height between the two sections ($H_1 - H_2$)

should be zero, and an acceptable maximum filling height difference is 30 mm.[12,13]

J-Ring Test

J-Ring test is used to evaluate the flowing ability and segregation of the self-compacting concrete. It is also to measure the level difference of concrete. The level difference in concrete does not exceed more than 10mm. The property of self-compacting concrete mainly depends on the number of finer materials present in

concrete. The lower percentage of addition of fiber gives the better result compared to other proportions. In J-Ring test were conducted for various mix proportions and the value obtained for control standard is 6.25mm. Thus, the J-Ring value is constantly increasing. The flowing ability of self-compacting concrete is influenced by increasing fiber content.[14]

**HARDEN CONCRETE TEST
Compressive Strength**

Compressive strength is one of the most significant and widely used characteristics of concrete. In most structural applications, concrete is primarily

designed to withstand compressive stresses. Even in situations where tensile or shear strength is the main concern, compressive strength is commonly used as an indicator of these properties.[15,16]

The overall results show that the compressive strength gradually increased 0.15% -1.00% of addition of fiber. Then the compressive strength gradually decreased.

Split Tensile Strength

The tensile strength of concrete is one of the basic and important properties. Split tensile strength on cylindrical specimens is method to determine the tensile strength of concrete. We know that concrete weak in tension due to its brittle nature and it not expected to resist direct tension. The direct measurement of tensile strength of concrete is difficult. Testing apparatus have been designed which assure uniform distribution of the pull applied to the concrete. This also sometimes referred as Brazilian test. The test carries out placing the cylindrical specimen horizontally between the loading surfaces of a compression testing machine and the load is applied until the failure of cylinder along vertical diameter. The split tensile strength test shows the 0.75% of addition of sisal fiber gives good results compared to other proportions.

These tests are conducted on specimens with different proportions in addition of sisal fiber. In 28 days of curing 0.75% of addition of fiber gives good split tensile strength. After that the strength of concrete gradually decreased.[17]

Flexural strength (Prism)

Flexural strength represents one aspect of the tensile capacity of concrete. It indicates the ability of an unreinforced concrete beam or slab to resist bending failure. This property is determined by testing a concrete beam subjected to loading over a span that is at least three times its depth. Flexural strength is expressed in terms of the modulus of rupture and typically ranges from about 10 to 20 percent of the compressive strength, depending on the type, size, and quantity of coarse aggregate

used. The test carried out various proportions. In curing process, the comparison of a flexural strength in control standard & mix proportion is tabulated and it shows that in SC₃ proportion is increased in 7 days of curing, in SC₄ proportion is increased in 14 days and 28 days of curing. Thus, overall result shows that the flexural strength gradually increases to steadily decrease.[18]

Poisson's Ratio

This test carries out for cylindrical specimen. When compressive force acts on a specimen then with increase in force, two types of strains that will crop in the specimen of concrete. Both strains are opposite in direction; one is along x-axis that is longitudinal strain and another one is along y-axis that is lateral strain.

The above graph mentions Poisson's ratio of the various types mix proportions. The specimens are cured for 14 days and 28 days. In 14 days of curing the poison ratio gradually increased at 0.75%-1.00%. Then the results suddenly decreased. In 28 days of curing the gradual increase of poisons ratio for the proportion of (SC₃-SC₄). Further mix proportions the results gradually decreased.[19]

Impact strength of cylinder

The cylinder having a diameter of 100mm and height of 50mm. Specimens are curing 28 days and subjected to impact test. They were placed on the base plate of impact testing machine and were then struck with repeated blows. A 44.5N hammer was dropped repeatedly from a height of 457mm into a 63.5 mm steel ball situated in the middle of the disc's upper surface to apply the impact load. The initial and final cracks should be carefully noted.

The table shows the impact energy of the different mix proportions. The number of blows required to identify the initial and final cracks are carefully noted. For

conventional concrete the initial crack attains for 5 blows and final cracks found at 7 blows. The maximum strain of energy observed is the proportion of (SC₄) 1.00% of the additional sisal fiber. The maximum

value of impact strain energy is 33.48kNmm. Impact strength increased 2.5 times of conventional concrete. Results show the impact energy gradually increased and suddenly decreased.[20]

Mix	Initial crack (N1)	Final crack (N2)	Drop hammer weight (gm)	Drop height (mm)	Impact energy (KN/mm)
CC	5	7	4400	457	13.78
SC ₁	5	6	4400	457	11.81
SC ₂	6	8	4400	457	15.75
SC ₃	7	13	4400	457	25.60
SC ₄	8	17	4400	457	33.48
SC ₅	5	8	4400	457	15.75
SC ₆	2	6	4400	457	11.81

Impact Strength on Slab

The behavior of the material at greater deformation speeds is ascertained through impact testing. This is designed to determine how a specimen of a known material will respond to suddenly applied stress. The test as certain whether the material is tough or brittle.[21]

The slab of concrete is cast in the size of 2 feet x 2 feet. The impact test on concrete is cast out drop weight impact machine. The number blows required to produce the crack concrete is calculated. The weight of the drop hammer is 83.385 N and height of the drop hammer is 850mm. The impact test is used to determine the impact energy of the concrete subjected to impact load.

Mix	No. of blows	Drop hammer weight (N)	Drop height (mm)	Impact energy (KN/mm)
CC	17	83.385	850	11.80
SC ₁	20	83.385	850	13.88
SC ₂	19	83.385	850	13.19
SC ₃	22	83.385	850	15.27
SC ₄	26	83.385	850	18.05
SC ₅	16	83.385	850	11.10
SC ₆	15	83.385	850	10.41

After the completion of curing process, the specimens are subjected to impact test. The impact test is carried out different types of mix proportions. The number of blows required to collapse the specimens are noted. The maximum impact strain energy is attained at 1.00% of addition of sisal fiber. The maximum value is 18.05kNmm. Conventional concrete has minimum value compared to sisal fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete. The impact energy of concrete specimens was tested by hammer which dropped from

considerable height. The impact strength of concrete gradually increased while adding the sisal fiber. Then the further percentage of addition of sisal fiber decreases the impact energy of the concrete slab specimens.

Flexural strength (Beam)

The flexural strength of 0.7m beam is carried out to determine the toughness of concrete with reinforcing steel. The test was carried out for loading frame. Ultimate load is used to determine the

flexural strength of beam. Centre deflection of beam is calculated at certain interval of application of load acting on the concrete beam. The load acting on each deflection is noted by using digital load cell. The flexural strength of beam is calculated at various mix proportions. Below graph shows the flexural strength of beam. The maximum strength attained at the two percentage such as 0.25% and 1.00% of the addition of sisal fiber. The sudden increase and decrease of the strength variation takes place.

Load vs Deflection

Load vs deflection plot is drawn for 0.7m beam. The strength behavior of the beam is plotted as follows. In this study the deflection and strength of the specimens are recorded. The deflection at mid span of the beam is calculated. The size of the specimen is 150mmx200mmx750mm. For conventional initial crack obtained at center is 2.8 tons. The ultimate load deflection at center is 7.52mm at the maximum load of 6.4 tons.

For 0.25% of addition of fiber the first crack appears at center is 1.2 ton. The center deflection is 12.7mm at the load of 4.4 ton.

For 0.5% of addition of fibers the initial crack is obtained in 2 ton. Ultimate load deflections are 8.23mm at the load of 6 ton.

For 0.75% of adding fiber the initial crack is found at the load 0.8ton. The ultimate load deflection is 5.5mm at the load of 7.2ton. The fibers are capable to arrest the cracks at certain limits.

For 1% of addition of fiber gives the better mechanical properties of concrete. The initial cracks are formed at the 4.4 ton; the maximum deflection of beam is 7.24 mm at the load of 6.4ton.

For 1.25% in addition the initial crack attains at the load 2 ton. The ultimate load that applied on the beam is 5.6-ton, maximum deflection is 5.44mm.

For 1.5% of addition of fibers initial crack obtain for the center 2.4ton. The ultimate load deflection for center is 3.72mm at the load of 5.2 ton.

Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity

The objective of this method is basically to measure the pulses of longitudinal vibrations passing through concrete. It was found that the velocity depended upon the elastic depend upon the elastic property geometry of the material. This test is used to find the quality of concrete without destroying the specimens.

The ultrasonic velocity is widely used non-destructive test to find the quality of concrete. The graph mentioned the ultrasonic pulse velocity of concrete at various days of curing such as 7, 14, and 28 days. The test is conducted as per IS13311 (part1)-1992 codal provision.

The higher ultrasonic pulse velocity value represents the good quality of concrete. The good quality of concrete attained 1.25% of additional fiber.

The above graph mentions the 14-day UPV value. The maximum velocity obtained at the proportion (SC3). The high velocity of pulse represents the quality of concrete is good. The graph below describes the 28-day UPV value. Ultrasonic pulse velocity test is the type of non-destructive test. It is a simple and quick test to identify the quality of concrete.

Rebound Hammer Test

The rebound hammer test is the type of non-destructive test which is used to determine the compressive strength of hardened concrete.

There are several types of hammers having varying impact energy from 0.07kgm to 3kgm, high impact energy used for mass concrete, where the concrete subjected to high impact forces. The low impact energy hammers are used for small and low strength materials. IS 13311 part 2 -1992 provides a correlation between the rebound number (RN) and the investigated concrete quality. Above graph shows that the rebound hammer test value at different mix proportions. Rebound hammer test is carried out after 14 and 28 days of curing.

CONCLUSION

The experiment is conducted on self-compacting concrete with addition of sisal fiber and found the strength comparison between conventional concrete and sisal fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete. In this experimental study, the addition of sisal fiber with concrete gives better results in impact tests. Impact energy calculated by the number of blows taken by concrete. In L-box test, sisal fiber is used as an admixture for maximum strength obtained is 0.99. In V-Funnel test when sisal fiber is used as an admixture for different proportion maximum strength obtained is 11 sec. For U-Box test, Sisal fiber is used at different proportions and the maximum value obtained is 25mm. For the same procedure J-Ring test is conducted and maximum value is obtained is 9mm.

In concrete sisal fiber is used as an admixture and compressive strength test were conducted for 7, 14 and 28 days of curing process according to the IS code procedure in 7 days of curing process the maximum value of compressive strength obtained is 19.55 N/mm².

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